

A Review of the Link Between Environmental Fluoride Exposure and Kidney Health: Implications for Chronic Kidney Disease of Unknown Etiology (CKDu)

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Abstract:

Fluoride is increasingly discussed as a geogenic risk factor for chronic kidney disease of uncertain etiology (CKDu), an epidemic of kidney disease affecting hot tropical farming communities worldwide. Emerging evidence continues to support the association between high fluoride exposure and kidney injury, particularly in regions with high fluoride levels. However, while fluoride's geogenic nature leads to prolonged exposure through water and food sources, the direct impact on kidney health remains incompletely understood. This review explores the relationship between fluoride exposure and adverse kidney health outcomes, especially in the context of CKDu, synthesizing findings from epidemiological studies conducted worldwide. While a broad range of studies show widespread dental fluorosis prevalence in regions with high environmental fluoride levels in Sri Lanka, India, China, and Mexico, such correlation was not evident for CKDu and environmental fluoride levels. Notably, the spatial distribution patterns of CKDu and exposure risk through high fluoride levels in drinking water exhibit some inconsistencies, suggesting fluoride alone may not be the sole driver of CKDu. This review underscores the kidney health risks of fluoride exposure while emphasizing the need for further studies that consider multiple interacting factors beyond fluoride exposure in examination of environmental triggers of CKDu.

Keywords: CKDu, Fluoride exposure, kidney injury, drinking water.

Introduction

Fluoride is a ubiquitous compound with sources ranging from drinking water to industrial processes, dental products, and certain food items. Communities worldwide are exposed to varying degrees of fluoride due to geographical, industrial, and lifestyle factors, thereby necessitating a comprehensive examination of its potential impact on health.

Fluoride exposure can occur through multiple routes. One of the primary sources of human exposure to fluoride is through drinking water. Fluoride levels in drinking water and other sources exhibit pronounced regional variations. Geological factors, such as the composition of underlying rocks and soil, play a crucial role in determining natural fluoride levels. Furthermore, anthropogenic activities and industrialization contribute to local variations in fluoride exposure (Shaji et al., 2024). Populations residing in regions with naturally occurring high fluoride levels in groundwater may experience elevated exposure, while others may encounter artificially increased levels due to fluoridation practices (Mukherjee and Singh, 2018). Industrial activities contribute to fluoride exposure through emissions and discharge. Certain industrial processes, such as phosphate fertilizer production and aluminum smelting, release fluoride into the surrounding environment. Proximity to such industries can result in heightened fluoride exposure for nearby communities (Choubisa and Choubisa, 2016). Dental products, including toothpaste and mouthwash, are also common sources of fluoride for individuals. While these products are essential for oral health, they contribute to systemic fluoride exposure, especially in cases of improper use or ingestion by children (Gupta et al., 2021). Food items, both natural and processed, can contain varying levels of fluoride (Bhattacharya et al., 2017). Certain crops accumulate fluoride from the soil (Rizzu et al., 2021), and the consumption of tea (Krishnankutty et al., 2022) and certain seafood (Rocha et al., 2013) can contribute significantly to dietary fluoride intake. Additionally, the use of fluoride-containing pesticides may further contribute to fluoride levels in food (Wang, Song and Wang, 2022).

Considering the multiple and ubiquitous sources of fluoride exposure, and the emerging evidence indicating a role for fluoride in chronic kidney disease outcomes, here we review (i) soil geochemistry and environmental fluoride (ii) regulatory thresholds for fluoride exposure (iii) health consequences of fluoride and (iv) risks to kidney health, including associations of fluoride exposure with prevalence of chronic kidney disease of unknown etiology (CKDu). We seek to provide a nuanced understanding of the current state of knowledge, identify research gaps, and offer insights that may inform public health policies and future investigations. In doing so, we aim to contribute to the ongoing dialogue surrounding CKDu and fluoride exposure, fostering a foundation for targeted interventions and improved health outcomes for affected populations.

Soil geochemistry and environmental fluoride

Fluorine, is an element lying in halogen series with distinct chemical properties owing to its high electronegativity. It frequently forms ionic compounds, especially with metals, and plays a significant role in biogeochemical systems (Atkins, De Paula and Keeler, 2023). Fluorine naturally occurs in the earth's crust in many mineral forms where fluorspar (CaF_2), fluorapatite [$3\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2\text{Ca}(\text{FCl}_2)$], cryolite (Na_3AlF_6) and sellaite (MgF_2) are the most prevalent fluoride minerals. The dissolution of fluoride minerals occurs slowly releasing fluoride ions into aquifers and soil making it available for uptake by plant and animals. Fluoride concentration

in aquifers depends on multiple factors such as fluoride content in surrounding rocks and minerals, soil geochemistry dependent mineral decomposition and dissolution rates, and percolation time of water within aquifers (Mohapatra et al., 2009; Bhatnagar, Kumar and Sillanpää, 2011).

Bioavailable fluoride contents in soil, ground and surface waters are largely dependent on soil the geochemistry of the rocks that shows a higher degree of regional variability. Particularly the presence of some host rocks (e.g., granite, alkali igneous rocks, gneisses, mica, shales, etc.) that composites fluoride containing minerals such as biotites, apatite, micas, and amphiboles directly contributes fluoride contents in aquifers (Bretzler and Johnson, 2015). A detailed representation of global geochemistry is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Regional geochemistry including the predominant rock types across the globe. Source: world geology compiled by the Geological Survey of Canada Published as Open-File Report 2915d. Available at: <https://mrdata.usgs.gov/geology/world/map-us.html> .

Compared to other rocks, igneous rocks contain higher amount of fluorine as magmas mostly contain fluorine in composition (Rosera et al., 2023). Moreover, groundwater chemistry, residence time, and hydrogeological conditions also contributes fluoride contents in aquifers along with the influence of environmental and climatic conditions (Akuno et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2021). Especially, temperature and pH of groundwater impacts the dissolution rates of fluoride minerals and rocks cation and anion exchange capacity of aquifer materials, precipitation, adsorption, and biochemical reaction (Mukherjee and Singh, 2018).

Apart from these natural processes, certain anthropogenic mediations such as fertilizer usage (eg. apatite), metal extraction, mining, and combustion of coal also contributes increased fluoride contents in ground water (Ayoob and Gupta, 2006) Thus, better understanding the dynamics of fluoride mobilization and the associated geographical and geochemical determinants become highly important in ensuring optimum fluoride exposure in communities.

Recommended fluoride intake levels and regulatory thresholds for fluoride

Intake of fluorides by humans primarily occurs through drinking water and food. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the occurrence of dental fluorosis is more likely when the drinking water fluoride content exceeds 1.5 ppm, whereas skeletal fluorosis is more likely when drinking water fluoride contents exceeds 3 ppm. As a protective measure against these health impacts, WHO recommends drinking water fluoride levels below 1.5 ppm .(Fawell et al., 2006).

Adhering to the WHO recommendation for drinking water fluoride content (1.5 ppm), the probability of high fluoride exposure in global communities is illustrated in figure 2 as per the predictive analysis by Podgorski & Berg, 2022 (Podgorski and Berg, 2022).

Figure 2: Probability of the likelihood of elevated fluoride contents in drinking water above the WHO recommendations in global perspective. Source: GAP, Groundwater Assessment Platform (2015), Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology (Eawag), Postfach 611, 8600 Dübendorf, Switzerland. www.gap.eawag.ch

According to the estimations of Podgorski & Berg, 2022, the population exposed to drinking water with fluoride concentrations above 1.5 ppm is represented in Figure 3. This estimation is based on random forest modelling for areas with a greater than 25% probability of incurring high fluoride in groundwater by multiplying the total population by the hazard percentage and the proportion of domestic water usage coming from untreated groundwater (Podgorski and Berg, 2022).

Figure 3: Estimated population potentially exposed to fluoride concentrations in drinking water greater than 1.5 mg/L (WHO recommendation). Source: GAP, Groundwater Assessment Platform (2015), Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology (Eawag), Postfach 611, 8600 Dübendorf, Switzerland. www.gap.eawag.ch

As implied by this recent estimation, hotspots of high risk of elevated fluoride exposure include central Australia, western North America, eastern Brazil, Africa, and multiple areas in Asia including India and Sri Lanka. Out of the total global population, 180 million people are likely to be exposed to high fluoride through drinking water where a majority of them resides in Asia (51-59 %) and Africa (37-46 %) (Podgorski and Berg, 2022).

Health consequences of fluoride

Human exposure to fluoride occurs mainly via drinking water while food, beverages, and oral care products may also act as potential sources. Exposure to fluoride at low levels can elicit beneficial effects on human health while this impact becomes deleterious at higher exposure levels (Jagtap et al., 2012). The prevalence of fluorine in both the environment and drinking water sources constitutes a primary factor in the occurrence of fluorosis.

For the teeth and bone development and prevention of dental caries, fluoride concentration of ~0.7 ppm in drinking water is considered beneficial. Hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3\text{OH}$) is a primary chemical constituent in teeth and bones. Due to the almost similar ionic radius, fluoride ions tend to replace hydroxide ions from hydroxyapatite forming fluoroapatite ($\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3\text{F}$). Because of the relatively higher hardness and toughness compared to hydroxy apatite, formation of fluoroapatite is known to make enamel harder to some extent making it more resistant to forming dental caries (Mohapatra et al., 2009). On the contrary, drinking water fluoride levels above 1.5 ppm are associated with adverse health effects on skeleton including skeletal fluorosis, osteoporosis, and arthritis (Miretzky and Cirelli, 2011). Longstanding exposures to higher fluoride contents results formation of fluoroapatite making bones harder, dense and brittle. Moreover, this level of exposure results in dental fluorosis characterized by

molting and embrittlement of teeth (Dissanayake, 1991). This condition poses a significant public health risk, emerging as a prominent medical issue in 24 countries. Recent research has increasingly revealed that exposure to fluoride not only harms bone tissue but also triggers various non-skeletal injuries, affecting systems such as the vascular, nervous, reproductive, and urinary systems (Kabir, Gupta and Tripathy, 2020).

Throughout the past few decades, a large number of studies have extensively investigated the adverse health outcomes associated with high fluoride exposure on human health and in laboratory animal models. However, most of these population health studies have focused on fluorosis in adult and children residing in regions with high geogenic fluoride levels, and does not provide comprehensive insight on kidney health impacts of high fluoride exposure. Laboratory studies with different animal models and *in-vitro* studies have provided insights into potentially toxic effects of fluoride exposure. However, the doses of exposure in many of these studies are higher than those environmentally relevant levels. As implied by these studies, exposure to elevated fluoride levels is supposed to elicit a number of detrimental health effects including structural and functional impairments in soft tissues, gastrointestinal system, brain and liver along with cytotoxicity, neurotoxicity, hypersensitivity and immunotoxicity, genotoxicity, carcinogenicity in multiple organs, developmental effects, disruptions in production and secretion of the thyroid hormones (Kabir, Gupta and Tripathy, 2020).

Fluoride exposure and adverse kidney health outcomes

Kidney tissues are likely susceptible to high fluoride exposure and toxicity. For instance, a study with 60 healthy adults above 20 years of age living in high (3.05 ppm) and low (0.04 ppm) drinking water fluoride contents in Nicaragua observed significant associations between exposure to high fluoride concentrations in drinking water and concentrations of fluoride in urine. Fluoride contents in urine ($\rho = 0.730$, $p < 0.001$), plasma ($\rho = 0.729$, $p < 0.001$), fasting whole saliva ($\rho = 0.653$, $p < 0.001$), and hair ($\rho = 0.603$, $p < 0.001$) were reported. Moreover, moderate positive associations were identified with fluoride contents in fingernail ($\rho = 0.502$, $p < 0.001$) and toenail ($\rho = 0.556$, $p < 0.001$) (Idowu et al., 2021). According to this study, urine serves as the most reliable indicator for biomonitoring of environmental fluoride exposures, while also indicating that the renal system is likely to be highly susceptible to fluoride exposure.

Fluoride is absorbed through the stomach and small intestine and circulated through the body storing some fraction in the bones and teeth, while most of the ingested fluoride is excreted via urine (Kabir, Gupta and Tripathy, 2020). Even the fluoride stored in the bones can be re-released and excreted via the urine. Therefore, the renal system is susceptible to high fluoride exposure and its toxic effects. Notably, fluoride has the potential to form complexes with essential metals, such as calcium and magnesium, disrupting normal cellular processes that may affect renal reabsorption processes, further exerting kidney toxicity.

As evidenced by animal studies including zebra fish (Yang et al., 2022), rats (Song et al., 2014), mice (Chattopadhyay et al., 2011), and rabbits (Sun et al., 2014), elevated fluoride exposure is associated with a number of deformities in renal structure characterized by shrunken and lobulated appearance of a glomerulus, dilated renal tubule, infiltration of inflammatory cells in renal tissues, vacuolar degeneration of tubular epithelium (Kabir, Gupta and Tripathy, 2020). Moreover, high fluoride exposure also accounts structural alterations of proximal, distal, and collecting tubules (Samantha, Bandyopadhyay and Das, 2016).

At the subcellular level, fluoride exposure can lead to oxidative stress, inflammation, and apoptosis. Fluoride exposure, especially at higher concentrations, is known to result in induction of oxidative stress, induction of lipid peroxidation, and decreased antioxidant capacity impacting the redox hemostasis in kidney. Elevated levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS), including superoxide anions and hydrogen peroxide, have been observed in response to fluoride exposure. These reactive species can lead to lipid peroxidation, DNA damage, and protein oxidation in renal cells leading to cell damage (Barbier, Arreola-Mendoza and Del Razo, 2010) and apoptosis. Fluoride exposure has been linked to the activation of apoptotic pathways in renal cells. Studies suggest that fluoride-induced apoptosis contributes to the disruption of normal cellular turnover in the kidneys, potentially leading to structural and functional damage (Barbier, Arreola-Mendoza and Del Razo, 2010). Fluoride exposure has also been shown to induce inflammatory responses in renal tissues. Pro-inflammatory cytokines and pathways are activated, contributing to the inflammatory cascade. Chronic inflammation is recognized as a key contributor to kidney damage and dysfunction.

Population health studies on fluoride exposure and kidney health outcomes

A growing body of research has investigated the relationship between elevated fluoride levels in drinking water and adverse kidney health outcomes within various communities worldwide. This section presents an overview of key studies conducted in India, Mexico, and China as examples to highlight kidney health implications of high fluoride exposure.

In India, due to higher fluoride contents in ground water, 21 states out of 35 states are known to have endemic fluorosis (Susheela et al., 2014; Quadri et al., 2016). Relatively higher fluoride exposure levels have been identified in children and adults in multiple communities across different regions in India along with evidence of dental fluorosis. A case-control study with 824 school children (8-15 years of age) from 10 schools in Doda district of Jammu and Kashmir states in India revealed a significant risk of kidney injury with high fluoride exposure. These researchers selected 8 schools from high fluoride regions with evidence of dental fluorosis where drinking water fluoride content ranged between 1.43 and 3.84 mg/L, along with a control group representing 2 schools in low fluoride regions (drinking water fluoride content below 1 mg/L). Dental fluorosis was identified in different grades in more than 95% of the affected regions. Urinary fluoride level of affected group (3.28 ± 1.71 mg/L) was significantly higher compared to the control group (1.91 ± 0.64 mg/L). The mean serum creatinine level (0.85 ± 0.35 mg/dL) of the affected children was significantly high compared to the control (0.45 ± 0.16 mg/dL). Moreover, mean eGFR of the affected children (84.1 ± 33.1 mL/min/1.73m²) was significantly lower compared to the control (120.9 ± 27.4 mL/min/1.73m²). These findings suggest a link between high fluoride exposure and potential kidney injury in children (Khandare, Gourineni and Validandi, 2017).

A biopsy study with Indian children with nephrotic syndrome lead characterization of microscopic evidence of kidney injury linked with high fluoride exposure. The participants represented three groups; high exposure patient group (urine fluoride level 4.01 ± 1.83 ppm), normal fluoride patient group (0.61 ± 0.17 ppm), and healthy control group (urinary fluoride level 0.56 ± 0.15 ppm). Compared to the normal fluoride group, apoptosis was observed at increased level in high fluoride excretion group. Furthermore, tubular epithelial damage associated with high fluoride exposure was observed in multiple forms including cell swelling

and lysis, cytoplasmic vacuolation, nuclear condensation, apoptosis, and necrosis (Quadri et al., 2018).

Another study with 842 young children in three Indian villages identified notably higher incidence of dental fluorosis: 51.90 % in Jhajjar, 94.63 % in Dadanpur and 36.84 % in Dariyapur. Significant, positive correlations of fluorosis with serum and urinary fluoride levels, and drinking water fluoride levels were observed (Kumar et al., 2017). A similar study with 139 school children from two villages (Gobindanagar and Bhagabandh) in Purulia District of West Bengal in India, identified dental fluorosis in 36.9% of children within the age range 12-14 years. Urinary fluoride ranges in children with dental fluorosis in Gobindanagar and Bhagabandh were 0.08-6.7 mg/L and 1.5-7.9mg/L respectively. However, none of these studies assessed kidney health of the participants.

In many regions of Mexico, higher fluoride exposures with evidence of dental fluorosis and adverse kidney health outcomes in adults and children are reported. A cross-sectional study with 239 adult residents from three municipalities in Chihuahua, México reported potential associations of fluoride exposure with kidney injury. The mean fluoride contents in drinking water and urine were 1.5 (0.19-1.8) ppm and 2.0 (1.1- 3.5) ppm respectively. Nearly 51% of samples reported fluoride levels above 1.5 ppm. Moderate and severe dental fluorosis was observed in 18.7% of participants. Multiple linear regression models identified a positive association of urinary fluoride level with multiple urinary markers including albumin ($\beta = 0.56$, $p < 0.001$), cystatin-C ($\beta = 0.022$, $p = 0.001$), KIM-1 ($\beta = 0.048$, $p = 0.008$), osteopontin ($\beta = 0.38$, $p = 0.041$), and eGFR ($\beta = 0.49$, $p = 0.03$) suggesting a potential link between fluoride exposure and kidney injury. However, this study has not investigated the variation of urinary biomarkers across different fluoride exposure levels (Jiménez-Córdova et al., 2018).

A similar cross-sectional study with 374 school children from the municipalities of Hidalgo del Parral and Aldama in Chihuahua in México reported supportive findings to above observations. In the region with high F exposure, the mean (IQR) fluoride levels in drinking water and urine were 1.93 (0.3–2.1) and 2.7 (2.0–3.6) ppm respectively with prevalence of 41.7% of dental fluorosis. In multiple linear regression models, urinary F was positively associated with eGFR ($\beta = 1.3$, $p = 0.015$), uCys-C ($\beta = -8.5$, $p = 0.043$), VCAM-1 ($\beta = 111.1$, $p = 0.019$), ICAM-1 ($\beta = 57$, $p = 0.032$) and cIMT ($\beta = 0.01$, $p = 0.032$). An inverse association was observed with uCys-C ($\beta = -8.5$, $p = 0.043$) and sCys-C ($\beta = -9.6$, $p = 0.021$), and no significant associations with ET-1 ($\beta = 0.069$, $p = 0.074$) and KIM-1 ($\beta = 29.1$, $p = 0.212$) were found. KIM-1 is a sensitive indicator of kidney injury, but the authors did not identify significant positive association of urinary F with KIM-1. Hence, this study does not provide strong evidence of kidney injury linked with fluoride exposure (Jiménez-Córdova et al., 2019).

Multiple regions in China have also been identified with higher geogenic fluoride contents with adverse health impacts to residential communities. A cross-sectional study with 1,070 adults (mean \pm SD age was 58.21 \pm 10.87 years) representing four villages in Wenshui County, Shanxi Province in China investigated kidney health outcomes linked with fluoride exposure using urinary NAG, serum RBP, serum Urea, serum C3, serum UA, and serum α 1-MG. The mean urinary fluoride concentration was 1.62 mg/L. Positive correlations of urinary fluoride concentrations were identified with both urinary NAG and serum urea. In adjusted regression models, a 1 mg/L increment of urinary fluoride was associated with 1.583 U/L increase in urinary NAG and 0.199 mmol/L increase in serum urea (Wu et al., 2021).

Chronic Kidney Disease of Uncertain Etiology and fluoride exposure

Chronic Kidney Disease of Uncertain Etiology (CKDu) presents a complex health challenge, casting a shadow over diverse populations in disparate regions. This condition is characterized by a progressive decline in kidney function without definitive causative factors and devoid of traditional risk factors such as diabetes and hypertension. CKDu has manifested in hotspots across the globe, from the rice paddies of Sri Lanka to the sugarcane fields of Central America posing a substantial challenge to healthcare systems worldwide. The prevalence of CKDu exhibits notable geographical heterogeneity, with hotspots identified in Sri Lanka, Mesoamerica, and parts of India.

Figure 4: Global prevalence of CKDu: Currently identified hotspots and regions with emerging evidence for the presence of CKDu (Gunasekara et al., 2020).

Interestingly, the confined nature of observed geographical and socio-economic CKDu disease patterns implies geo-environmental and/or occupational risk factors (Chandrajith et al., 2011). This regional heterogeneity of CKDu reveals a spectrum of unique factors including chronic exposure to nephrotoxic elements such as toxic heavy metals and agrochemical residues during farming activities (Jayatilake et al., 2013; Jayasumana, Gunatilake and Senanayake, 2014; Jayasumana et al., 2015; Jayasumana, Gunatilake and Siribaddana, 2015; Ulrich et al., 2023; Chandrajith et al., 2024); long-term consumption of untreated groundwater that is rich in harmful chemical and microbiological contaminants (Dharma-wardana et al., 2015; Jayasumana et al., 2015; Wasana et al., 2016; Babich et al., 2020); occupational exposure to heat stress under the hot climatic conditions prevail in the dry zone, and subsequent low water intake leading to dehydration (Herath et al., 2018; Jayasekara et al., 2019). Importantly, some of these factors may interact with fluoride in the environment and within an individual, amplifying or mitigating the impact of fluoride exposure on CKDu incidence. Understanding the regional nuances is pivotal for developing targeted interventions and preventive measures tailored to the specific challenges faced by each community.

The potential link between fluoride and CKDu has gained prominence in recent years with studies from diverse regions providing evidence. Fluoride exposure through drinking water has been a subject of considerable concern regarding its impact on kidney health in various regions, with many studies based in Sri Lanka. The subsequent section summarizes multiple studies aiming to contextualize the potential association between fluoride exposure and CKDu.

Evidence for an association between CKDu and fluoride exposure from epidemiological studies and hydrological studies

A case-control study identified 116 non-dialysis CKDu subjects (aged between 19 and 76 years) verified through biopsies, from Girandurukotte and Wilgamuwa renal clinics along with 77 age-matched controls. Compared to the control group, serum and urinary fluoride levels of the CKDu patients were significantly higher. In CKDu patients, the mean fluoride levels in serum and urine were 1.39 ± 1.1 mg/L (range: 0.47-9.58 mg/L) and 1.53 ± 0.8 mg/L (range: 0.45-6.92 mg/L) respectively. To contrast, in the controls, the mean serum and urine fluoride levels were 1.07 ± 0.3 mg/L (range: 0.51-1.92 mg/L) and 1.26 ± 0.6 mg/L (range: 0.36-3.8 mg/L), respectively. Moreover, significant variation of urinary fluoride levels was observed with CKD stage in CKDu patients (Fernando et al., 2020).

A similar study with 311 biopsy-confirmed CKDu patients and 276 healthy controls in two CKDu impacted areas in Sri Lanka (Girandurukotte and Medawachchiya) also reported consistent findings (Nanayakkara et al., 2020). There, the researchers identified significantly elevated serum fluoride levels in CKDu patients at stages 2-5 compared to the healthy controls. Mean serum fluoride levels of the patients ranged between 0.035 mg/L and 0.124 mg/L, and serum fluoride levels increased with decreasing eGFR. Analysis of drinking water samples identified fluoride contents below the WHO recommended level (1.5mg/L) in 95% of the samples, suggesting little evidence for fluoride exposure through drinking water in the area (Nanayakkara et al., 2020). This study did not report details on urinary fluoride levels.

Another recent study in Moneragala District, identified prevalence of CKDu as 6.7 % following screening of 46,754 participants (Liyanage et al., 2022). The researchers analyzed drinking water samples from the wells utilized by CKDu patients and healthy individuals in the study area, and identified significantly higher levels of fluoride in well water consumed by CKDu patients compared to the wells utilized by healthy individuals. Higher fluoride levels above the recommended threshold (1 mg/L) were reported in 87% of the wells utilized by CKDu patients. Furthermore, significantly higher concentrations of multiple metal ions (Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+}) were identified in well water consumed by CKDu patients. However, the concentrations of As, Pb, and Cd remained at permissible limits in all wells. According to the researchers, higher fluoride contents and increased hardness in water are likely contributing to CKDu incidence in the area (Liyanage et al., 2022).

In a study within CKDu affected and nonaffected communities within the North Central Province of Sri Lanka, fluoride levels were above the WHO recommended limits in most of the locations within the CKDu affected areas compared to the control areas (Wasana et al., 2016). Levels of Cd, As and Al in water were found comparable across all study regions and remained below WHO permitted levels (3 ppb for Cd and 10 ppb for As). Although a positive correlation of drinking water fluoride concentration with the prevalence of CKDu was identified, the prevalence of CKDu was low in certain regions with high fluoride contents. (Wasana et al., 2016).

Studies in CKDu endemic and non-endemic regions in Sri Lanka, have reported mixed findings on nephrotoxic ion levels in drinking water sources. For instance, a study in Wewelketiya (a CKDu-endemic region in North Central Province) identified Cd (60% of samples) and Pb (40 % of samples) in water samples above the recommended limits in Sri Lanka, but below the maximum permissible limits. Moreover, in 80% of the water samples collected in this study area and surrounding control areas reported fluoride levels above permissible limits.

Considering these findings, the levels of heavy metals and metalloids typically considered nephrotoxic (eg. Cd, As, Pb) are reported in drinking water below WHO permitted limits, along with fluoride levels above WHO permitted limits in certain regions with high burden of CKDu. These observations may add credence to the hypothesis that fluoride is a driver of CKDu in these regions.

In 2019, Balasooriya et al, conducted investigations on fluoride and hardness in relation to CKDu prevalence in Ginnoruwa area, which is a known hotspot of CKDu in Sri Lanka. This study compared drinking water fluoride and hardness in water samples collected from wells utilized by CKDu patients in the area along with those from the wells utilized by the healthy individuals in close proximity. The analysis identified significantly higher levels of pH, total hardness, electrical conductivity, and several ions (calcium, magnesium, fluoride, chloride, phosphate and sulphate) in drinking water samples from the wells utilized by CKDu patients compared to the controls. The presence of As, Cd, and Pb showed no significant difference between the two types of wells, while the concentrations of these ions remained below the WHO recommended limits (Balasooriya et al., 2020). A detailed interpretation on the distribution pattern of drinking water fluoride and magnesium levels with CKDu prevalence is given in figures 2,4, and 5 as produced in this study (Balasooriya et al., 2020).

According to the interpretations of this study, researchers suggest that drinking water fluoride and hardness may act synergistically contributing kidney injury and progression of kidney damage (Balasooriya et al., 2020). As it appears in the ground water fluoride distribution map (Figure 4 in the publication by Balasooriya et al. 2020), a majority of the wells of CKDu patients are located in high fluoride areas. However, there are some wells utilized by healthy subjects remains at very close proximity to the wells utilized by CKDu patients with more consistent fluoride and magnesium contents. Hence, to gain more precise insights on the association of fluoride and hardness, a careful consideration of the other exposures and lifestyle practices of the participants are required.

A similar hydrological investigation was conducted by Botheju et al., in Girandurukotte (a CKDu impacted region in Badulla District) *grama niladhari* division (GND) along with a control area, Dambethalawa GND (CKDu non prevalent region in Ampara District) in Sri Lanka. Elevated fluoride levels above the recommended thresholds were observed in 81% of water samples in CKDu affected region (range: 0.244 – 5.743 ppm) while this percentage was 28% in CKDu non-affected regions. A higher degree of water hardness was identified in CKDu impacted region (22.98 – 174.01 ppm) while soft water was identified in the control region. (Figure 6 in the original publication) (Botheju, Liyanage and Kannangara, 2021).

Moreover, analysis of water samples revealed significantly higher concentrations of nephrotoxic ions Cd (9.78–187.25 ppb), Pb (0.08–0.66 ppb), As (20.76–103.30 ppb), and Cr (0.03–0.34 ppm) (Figure 3) (Botheju, Liyanage and Kannangara, 2021).

According to Botheju, et al., prolonged exposure to nephrotoxic ions, high fluoride, and hardness may contribute to CKDu in affected regions (Botheju, Liyanage and Kannangara, 2021). However, this study has not incorporated the residences of CKDu patients along with the geospatial map of fluoride, hardness, and nephrotoxic ion concentrations in Girandurukotte *grama niladhari* division. Furthermore, when taking a closer look at the geospatial distribution of the studied risk factors, there are some inconsistencies. For instance, in the regions with highest levels of fluoride, water hardness remains low and warrants a correlation analysis to examine how these factors present a risk to kidney health. Additionally, further studies are need to examine the role of Cd, Pb, As, and Cr as potential nephrotoxicants when in mixture even at low-levels. Relatedly, geographic areas where most of these risk factors unite are identified as CKDu hotspots, indicating the need for further studies to comprehensively examine the role of synergistic effects of environmental exposures.

Another recent study analyzed 154 water samples collected from wells located in CKDu endemic regions along with 50 water samples collected from wells in CKDu non-prevalent regions in Sri Lanka. Glyphosate contamination was detected in 44% of endemic wells and 8% of nonendemic wells while fluoride was detected in 99% of endemic wells and 80% of nonendemic wells. According to logistic regression, the presence of elevated glyphosate, fluoride, hardness, and vanadium in wells was positively associated with CKDu prevalence. The co-occurrence of glyphosate and high hardness indicate potential complexation of glyphosate in wells from CKDu-endemic areas and indicate that fluoride alone may not be sufficient to drive CKDu (Ulrich et al., 2023).

Perera et al., 2021 conducted a similar study to evaluate the contamination status of heavy metals/metalloids of the drinking water and agricultural soil in two *grama niladhari* divisions in CKDu endemic areas (Eppawala and Ambagaswewa) in the north Central Province in comparison to a control GND (Dambethalawa) in Ampara district in Sri Lanka. Mean drinking water fluoride levels in CKDu endemic GNDs: Eppawala (1.87 ppm; range: 0.09-3.98 ppm) and Ambagaswewa (1.72 ppm; range: 0.05-4.00 ppm) were markedly high compared to the control area (0.40 ppm; range: 0.10-1.10 ppm). According to the analysis, the concentrations of Cd, As, Pb, Cr, Cu, and Zn in drinking water samples collected from both CKDu endemic regions remained below the recommended thresholds. However, geoaccumulation indices of soil from paddy farming fields revealed moderate contamination of soil with As, Pb, Cu, Ni, Cr, Zn, and Cd. According to the researchers, application of fertilizers, which contained a high dose of toxic metals, and extensive application of low-quality fertilizers could be the driving force for agricultural soil pollution in these CKDu impacted regions (Perera et al., 2021).

Although the contents of these nephrotoxic metals and metalloids in drinking water samples in the CKDu impacted regions below the recommended thresholds, rigorous assessment of exposure risks in these communities through paddy and other food crops are required for having better conclusions on the impact of these ions on development and progression of kidney injury and subsequent CKDu susceptibilities.

A comparative survey on water quality in Thunukkai Divisional secretariat (a CKDu impacted region in Mullaitivu District in Sri Lanka) also identified elevated levels of fluoride (mean: 1.73 ppm, range: 0.1-22.3 ppm) and hardness (mean: 295.76 ppm, range: 39-683 ppm) in drinking water samples (Gobalarajah et al., 2020). Moreover, exceeding the established standards in Sri Lanka, the water samples reported elevated levels of fluoride (39.5%),

hardness (65.4%), arsenic (23.4%), chloride (31.42%), and nitrate (15.2%), when taken as a percentage of the total number of water samples collected, arsenic content and total hardness showed positive correlations with serum creatinine in CKDu patients in the area (Gobalarajah et al., 2020).

Another analysis of water samples in 34 wells (27 dug wells and 7 tube wells) in Anuradhapura in Sri Lanka district identified elevated total dissolved solid and magnesium levels exceeding the maximum allowable limits exclusively in the high risk areas of CKDu showing significant associations of water hardness and ionicity in groundwater with the incidence of CKDu (Imbulana, Oguma and Takizawa, 2020). Moreover, a separate study with 60 water samples in Anuradhapura district found that water quality parameters including alkalinity, TDS, hardness, and magnesium were not significantly affected by the seasonal variations of rainfall in the area leading to their presence at higher levels in well water throughout the year (Imbulana, Oguma and Takizawa, 2021).

Uva province is another region in Sri Lanka where CKDu is reported among farming communities in Sri Lanka. A recent study with 260 groundwater samples collected from Uva province adhering to a systematic random sampling method, identified low fluoride level (mean <1 ppm) in water samples with relatively low hardness (mean±SD: 234±170 ppm) compared to the levels reported in North central province. However, 67% of the dug wells and 59.7% of the tube wells reported fluoride contents above the threshold of 1.5 ppm in water showing a likelihood of high fluoride exposures within the communities. In logistic regression models, fluoride and phosphate in ground water had significant associations with the progression of CKDu among the inhabitants (Piyathilake et al., 2021). In addition, a number of hydrological investigations in CKDu impacted regions in Sri Lanka have evidenced the presence of fluoride, hardness and a number of cations and anions at elevated levels compared to the drinking water samples in CKDu non-prevalent regions in the country (Chandrajith et al., 2011; 2024; Dharma-wardana et al., 2015; Herath et al., 2017; Fernando et al., 2022; Sandanayake et al., 2023; Shi et al., 2023). Considering the evidence reported in these hydrological investigations, the presence of such ions at elevated levels, exceeding the recommended levels is discussed as a potential factor that contributes kidney injury and CKDu in localized hotspots. Importantly, the synergetic impact of these ionic combinations in drinking water needs further studies to determine the mechanistic basis of kidney injury associated with these ions in relation to CKDu.

Apart from Sri Lanka, several studies have also investigated associations of high fluoride exposure and kidney health. A study analyzed composite groundwater sampling collected from 40 selected villages in Uddanam and 100 villages of other nine districts in Andhra Pradesh, both in India (Lal et al., 2020). Higher incidence of acidity in drinking water (pH < 6.5) was observed in Uddanam area. During the dry season, elevated lead contents exceeding the threshold of 0.01 ppm given by Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) was identified in 55% of the villages while during the wet season, while this incidence dropped to 10% in the wet season. However, ground water fluoride levels were found well below the BIS standard (1.5 ppm) in 95 % of the villages (mean concentration was 0.54 ppm, SD = 0.40 ppm). Moreover, the presence of pesticides was not identified in any groundwater sample while phthalates were detected in all samples (Lal et al., 2020). Odisha is another region in India with high burden of CKDu. Analysis of ground water samples in the area identified elevated fluoride levels above the WHO threshold (1.5 ppm) in 57 % of drinking water samples with average fluoride content

of 1.8 ppm (range: 0.58 – 4.95 ppm). Health risk assessment based on exposure pathways through ingestion and dermal contact identified a higher risk of non-carcinogenic health problems associated with high fluoride exposure particularly for infants and children (Mohanty et al., 2023).

In summary, multiple studies in Sri Lanka indicate a moderate to a strong association with fluoride exposure risk and CKDu. However, such an association is not clear in India and other CKDu hotspots worldwide. Notably, several studies have found the presence of nephrotoxic heavy metals and metalloids in environmental samples in CKDu impacted regions and in biospecimen of CKDu patients at elevated levels compared to healthy subjects.

Evidence from autopsy/biopsy studies

A case-control study compared autopsy samples of bones from patients who died of CKDu in CKDu impacted regions with samples from age-matched control subjects with no history of kidney disease who died in CKDu non-prevalent regions (Jayalal et al., 2020). In this study, while marked differences of cadmium and mercury contents was not observed between the two groups, calcium-adjusted lead and fluoride levels in bones of CKDu cases were significantly higher compared to the control group. This indicates a potentially higher exposure to lead and fluoride. (Jayalal et al., 2020). It is important to note that gradual reduction of glomerular filtration rate (GFR) may have occurred with CKDu progression. At a certain point of the threshold of low GFR, excretion of fluoride may have been impaired, since the main excretory pathway of fluoride is via the kidneys. Fluoride accumulation in bones and re-release into the blood in turn may further exacerbate nephrotoxicity, triggering a synergistic cascade of events which may lead to a further deterioration in the GFR.

Spatial distribution of Fluoride and CKDu prevalence

Considering the emerging evidence from Sri Lanka showing a correlation between fluoride exposure and CKDu, examination of spatial overlap of fluoride distribution and CKDu prevalence can be insightful. In Sri Lanka, a clear overlap between spatial distribution of fluoride and CKDu epidemiology can be observed (Figure 5). However, the spatial distribution patterns of fluoride in distinct geographical areas in India does not show strong overlap with prevalence of CKDu as shown in Sri Lanka. For instance, the prevalence of CKDu within the southern part of India as illustrated in the figure 1 of the publication by Parameswaran et al., (Parameswaran et al., 2020) does not show strong overlap with the fluoride distribution map illustrated in Figure 2 in research article by Mukherjee and Singh, 2018 (Mukherjee and Singh, 2018).

Figure 5: Spatial distribution of (a) fluoride and (b) CKD/CKDu prevalence in Sri Lanka based on cases reported at Divisional Secretariat levels as analyzed by Ranasinghe, et al., 2019.

As it is indicated in the original article, the prevalence of CKDu in the region where the highest fluoride content is reported is at the lowest, while the fluoride content in the areas where highest prevalence of CKDu is reported, appears relatively low. For instance, the northern part including the territory of Delhi in India CKDu is rarely reported, although the fluoride content is relatively high. On the contrary, in certain geographies with higher fluoride contents, CKDu is observed at higher prevalence rates.

Conclusion

Population health studies in regions with elevated drinking water fluoride levels underscore its association with detrimental effects on both children and adults, notably evidenced by the prevalence of dental fluorosis. The widespread presence of dental fluorosis in regions such as India and China highlight the intensity of fluoride exposure. Furthermore, biomarker-based studies show a correlation between high fluoride exposure and kidney injury. However, in-depth studies with longitudinal data are required to understand the longstanding kidney health impacts of fluoride exposure, particularly in communities residing in regions with higher geogenic fluoride contents.

Taken together, studies summarized in this review from Sri Lanka suggest an association with fluoride exposure risk and CKDu incidence. Given the known nephrotoxic properties of fluoride, higher levels of this element, particularly in the drinking water could have contributed to kidney damage and initiation and/or progression of CKDu. However, it is important to note that the regional variations and diverse sources of fluoride presents a challenge in determining potential mechanisms that may underlie the observed associations with CKDu incidence. Adding to the complexities of this association is the methodological variations, conflicting findings, and the lack of standardized approaches. Most notably, this complexity is highlighted in the lack of association with fluoride exposure risk and CKDu in India.

Studies summarized here show that chronic fluoride exposure risk may have preceded the emergence of CKDu. For example, the presence of dental fluorosis has been documented in multiple regions across the globe including in some of the CKDu impacted areas for decades earlier than reports of CKDu. Importantly, almost all the research publications and case studies referring to CKDu emerged after 1990s and the prevalence of CKDu became increasingly evident after that in the currently known hotspots. If high fluoride exposure alone is responsible for CKDu, regions with high dental fluorosis would overlap with global CKDu hotspots and would have become evident much earlier than 1990s.

The lack of CKDu incidence in regions around the world with high risk of fluoride exposure indicates that while fluoride pose a risk to kidney health, other environmental triggers are also likely contributors to CKDu. Numerous studies have reported plausible evidence linking anthropogenic contaminants in the environment with the incidence of a variety of noncommunicable diseases including CKDu. It is plausible that CKDu is likely influenced by factors such as water hardness and fluoride, and contaminants such as heavy metals and agrochemicals are critical for disease initiation and progression. Thus, a comprehensive understanding of CKDu etiology necessitates consideration of multiple interacting factors and synergism between fluoride, water hardness, heavy metals and agrochemicals.

Despite mixed evidence for an association with CKDu and fluoride globally, regular monitoring and better management of water supplies in CKDu prevalent areas are crucial. For example, in Sri Lanka, according to the approximations by Ranasinghe et al., 2019, high fluoride levels in drinking water exceeding 1 ppm has affected 1.2 million (11.2 %) inhabitants. Moreover, 0.53 million (12%) of children below 12 years of age are living in high-fluoride areas (>1 ppm). In global perspective, the estimated risk of high fluoride exposure through drinking water (fluoride concentration above 1.5 ppm ranges between 63 and 330 million people (0.8% - 4.4 % of global population) according to a recent analysis (Podgorski and Berg, 2022). As implied by these statistics, high fluoride exposure through drinking water has impacted a significant portion of the country's population (Ranasinghe, Kruger and Tennant, 2019) in Sri Lanka alone. Hence, a global survey is required to investigate the health risks associated with fluoride exposure prioritizing the communities in regions where fluoride is reported at higher levels in drinking water and ground water.

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